

10.5281/zenodo.12162330

Vol. 07 Issue 05 May - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01435

WORK FLEXIBILITY PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORTS AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

By

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Abstract

The study investigated work flexibility practices and organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by three research questions and null three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised all the 7,027 teachers in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample size of 703 teachers was drawn for the study using proportionate stratified sampling technique. A researcher developed instruments titled "Work Flexibility Practices Scale (WFPS)", "Organizational Supports Scale (OSS)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded coefficient values of 0.78, 0.80 and 0.82 for WFPS, OSS and TJPQ respectively. The researcher together with three research assistants collected data for the study using the direct delivery method and 98% return was recorded. Simple regression was used to answer research questions and hypotheses 1 and 2, while multiple regression was used to answer the research question and hypothesis 3. The findings of the study revealed among others work flexibility practices is a strong and significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found out that organizational supports is a strong and significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education should develop policy that encourages principals to improve work flexibility practices for high job performance of teachers.

Keywords:

Work Flexibility, Organizational Supports, Teachers, Job Performance, Schools

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Introduction

School operates in a dynamic and complex environment that may bring about changes in the ways that works are done by members of staff to attain set goals. The dynamic nature of contemporary work setting of every educational institution or organization makes imperative for managers to put substantial efforts to help members of staff to adjust and cope to the evolving job demand and needs. In addition, work demands of teachers tend to conflict with a variety of personal and family responsibilities. Ajayi, Olaniyi and Abubakar (2022) opined that flexible work arrangements have emerged as a major problem in the workplace where official obligations and personal responsibilities conflict.

Work flexibility is concerned with granting freedom to staff to decide their job schedules and approaches. According to Dwianto, Darka and Widayatmoko (2023), work flexibility is the extent to which members of staff have the freedom to tailor their work arrangements to accommodate personal needs and preferences within the operational framework of organization. Work flexibility allows members of staff to carry their duties outside the normal job schedules. Anaja and Peter (2022) described work flexibility practices as arrangements that allow staff to exercise control over their job scheduling, location, procedures and time. It gives teachers the opportunity to choose where and when to carry out some duties within the framework of official job description. Work flexibility practice is defined by Tamunomiebi and Bassey (2020), as liberty to make arrangement in terms of working time, working location and pattern of working. Work flexibility is the process of granting autonomy to staff in carrying out their official responsibilities and activities. In modern workplaces, Chiekezie, Ohue and Ikhide (2024) noted that work flexibility entails providing employees (individually or collectively) with options and autonomy in managing their work schedules, location, and tasks. Work flexibility is conceptualized by Vito and Mekuri-Ndimele (2021), as act of granting authority to staff to choose where to work, for how long and the people to work with. Work flexibility practices involve allowing members of staff to decide when, where, and how to carry out their official duties.

Work flexibility practices could be considered in terms of time, place and amount of work to be done. Mekuri-Ndimele (2020) posited that the three major forms of work flexibility practices are: flexibility in the scheduling of hours, the place of work, and the numbers of work hours. Flexibility in the scheduling of hours is deciding tasks and periods to execute them either in a day, week or more. Flexibility in the place of work is carry out official duties at home and any location other than the school environment. Flexibility in the numbers of work hours is concerned with having control of the amount of work to start and complete task at a given time. Prasad and Mishra (2021) maintained that work flexibility covers hours to carry out tasks, the location and also includes the following; shift working, part-time, remote working/telecommuting, sabbatical/career break, flexi-time, job sharing, self-roistering, time off in lieu, vacation-time working among others. It enables the employees to adjust their personal and professional commitments according to the circumstances. Teachers who are granted work flexibility require the organizational supports to excel in discharging their duties.

Organizational supports are all forms of assistance and guidance provided for staff to motivate them in discharging their duties in the workplace. According to Wen, Siahaan, Anggraini and Sulaiman (2021), organizational supports are an employee's perception of the extent to which management values and cares about their welfare in the workplace. It entails appreciating the efforts of staff and showing care towards their professional problems. Prasetyo and Harsono (2023) maintained that members of staff will feel attached to the organization and try to give their best efforts to achieve organizational goals, when they receive adequate supports from the organization.

Organizational supports are efforts and programmes put in place to satisfy the professional, social and emotional needs of staff.

School management could render supports to teachers by providing resources, granting them access to information, offering counselling services and rendering other assistance required for them to effectively discharge their duties. In the same vein, Tamimi and Tamam (2023) asserted that organizational supports which could be provided in forms of providing proper benefits, creating good relations between superiors and subordinates, and providing adequate facilities are likely to create good working conditions to motivate members of staff to put substantial efforts in carrying out their duties. Organizational supports could be in form of organizing staff professional development programmes, providing clear communication channels, prioritizing well-being, making available mentorship opportunities and showing empathy to members of staff. Salau (2022) asserted that organizational supports also include providing opportunities for enhancing academic and professional qualification of staff, arranging seminars, enhancing promotion opportunities, making available incentives and other fringe benefits. Furthermore to this, the author maintained that organizational support can also include recognition of efforts, training, good reward, system and better work condition, fairness and managers support. Also, Agbasi, Onyekwelu and Nwosu (2023) pointed out that organizational supports could also take the form of a fair attitude, adequate income, favourable work arrangements, opportunities to engage in decision-making recognition of achievement and cordial interpersonal relationships. Appreciating teachers with gifts and awards could be forms of organizational supports to spur them to perform their job better. When teachers receive strong organizational supports, they are likely to feel appreciated which could boost their morale to work hard for desirable job performance.

Teachers' job performance is work-related activities undertaken by members of teaching staff to achieve predetermined goals. Teachers' job performance is described by Amaefule, Michael and Umeh (2024) as the actions carried out by teaching staff to fulfill responsibilities which aligned with daily classroom objectives and broader educational goals. Furthermore, Amaefule et al noted that these responsibilities may include effectively covering the designated curriculum, regularly assessing and grading student work, managing classroom behavior, and preparing lesson plans, among other tasks. It is the outcomes of the time and efforts made by members of teaching staff in discharging their responsibilities. It is the result obtained by teaching staff in carrying out their duties to achieve set goals. Teachers' job performance is the act of carrying out tasks in accordance with the work description to achieve predetermined goals.

There are some areas in which teachers seem to be underperforming their duties in public secondary schools in Anambra State. To buttress this, Ebiem and Ikediugwu (2023) noted that there are laxities in teachers' job performance as could be observed in their poor attitude to work, absenteeism, lack of dedication to teaching and carrying out assigned tasks in secondary schools in Anambra State. Similarly, Asiegbu and Emegwa (2024) observed that some teachers do not go to school on time, some rarely teach students and write notes of lesson in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These laxities in teachers' job performance could be connected to the rigid nature of teaching job and insufficient assistance received by teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Teachers are rarely exposed to intensive annual training programmes, their professional problems and welfare are not given desirable attention to improve their physical and emotional well-being in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Some teachers find it difficult to maintain a balance between official, personal and family responsibilities probably due to the rigid nature of teaching job in secondary schools. Chukwueze (2023) noted that most public secondary schools management styles and procedures to be followed by staff in performing duties in Anambra State are

rigid and obsolete in this contemporary workplace. These problems prompted the investigation into work flexibility practices and organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate work flexibility practices and organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to investigate:

1. Work flexibility practices as a predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Organizational supports as a predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Work flexibility practices and organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of association between work flexibility practices and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of association between organizational supports and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the predictive value of association between work flexibility practices, organizational supports and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Work flexibility practices is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Organizational supports is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Work flexibility practices and organizational supports are not significant predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was undertaken in Anambra State located in South Eastern part of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 7,027 teachers in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample size of 703 teachers was drawn for the study using proportionate stratified sampling technique.

A researcher developed instruments titled "Work Flexibility Practices Scale (WFPS)", "Organizational Supports Scale (OSS)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were developed by the researchers based on insight gained from literature review and opinions of experts. The first instrument titled WFPS had 12 items. The second instrument titled OSS contained 11 items, while the third instrument titled TJPQ has 22 items. The three sets of the instruments were structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree. The instruments were validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the

Department of Educational Foundations, NnamdiAzikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded coefficient values of 0.78, 0.80 and 0.82 for WFPS, OSS and TJPQ respectively.

The researcher together with three research assistants collected data for the study using direct delivery method. A total of 703 copies of instruments were distributed and 687 copies of questionnaires were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 98 percent return rate. Simple regression was used to answer research questions and hypotheses 1 and 2, while multiple regression was used to answer the research question and hypothesis 3. For the research questions the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient recommended by Schober, Boer and Schwarte (2018), as follows:

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .10	Negligible correlation
.11- .39	Weak correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if the exact p -value is equal to or greater than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted but if exact p -value is less than significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the predictive value of association between work flexibility practices and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Work Flexibility Practices as a Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Model	n	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Work Flexibility Practices	687	.765	.654	.653	.23314		Strong

Table 1 showed that correlation coefficient between work flexibility practices and teachers' job performance is 0.765 with a coefficient of determination of 0.654. This shows that work flexibility practices could explain 65.4% variation in job performance of teachers. The regression Coefficient r of 0.765 indicated that work flexibility practices is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of association between organizational supports and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Organizational Supports as a Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Model	n	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Organizational Supports	687	.799	.743	.742	.30021		Strong

As shown in Table 2, the correlation coefficient between organizational supports and teachers' job performance is 0.799 with a coefficient of determination of 0.743. This indicates that organizational supports could account for 74.3% changes in job performance of teachers. The regression Coefficient r of 0.779 indicated that organizational supports is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: What is the predictive value of association between work flexibility practices, organizational supports and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: The Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Work Flexibility Practices, Organizational Supports as Predictors of Teachers' Job Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	.804	.771	.770	.37654	Strong

Result in table 3 showed that the correlation coefficient of multiple regression analysis between work flexibility practices, organizational supports and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State is 0.804 with a coefficient of determination of 0.771. This shows that 77.1 % variation in teachers' job performance can be attributed to work flexibility practices and organizational supports. The regression Coefficient r of 0.804 indicated that work flexibility practices and organizational supports are strong predictors of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One: Work flexibility practices is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Work Flexibility Practices as Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Work Flexibility Practices	.765	.654	543.751	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 4, the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.765, while the R² is 0.654 showing that work flexibility practices make 65.4% contribution to the variance in teachers' job performance. The $F(1/687) = 543.751$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, work flexibility practices is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two: Organizational Supports is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Organizational Supports as Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Organizational Supports	.779	.743	407.171	.000	*S

*Significant

Result in Table 5 indicates that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.779, while the R^2 is 0.743 showing that organizational supports could account for 65.4% variance in teachers' job performance. The $F(1/687) = 407.171$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, organizational supports is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three: Work Flexibility Practices, Organizational Supports are significant predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Work Flexibility Practices and Organizational Supports as Significant Predictors of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R^2	F	P-value	Remark
Work Flexibility Practices and Organizational Supports	.804	.771	389.224	.000	*S

*Significant

Table 6 reveals that multiple regression coefficient (R) is 0.804, while the R^2 is 0.771 showing that work flexibility practices and organizational supports could account for 77.1% change in teachers' job performance. The $F(1/687) = 389.224$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, work flexibility practices and organizational supports are significant predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The result of the study revealed that work flexibility practices is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This supported the finding of Mekuri-Ndimele (2020) which showed that there is a strong positive relationship between work flexibility and employee performance. The possible explanation for this finding is that work flexibility practices create work-life balance which motivates teachers to improve their job performance. Work flexibility makes teachers feel valued which could boost their morale to work hard to improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Work flexibility enhances the use of initiatives which could account for the strong predictor of teachers' job performance. It was also discovered that work flexibility practices is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Ajayi, Olaniyi and Abubakar (2022) which indicated that a significant relationship existed between flexible work practices and employee performance. This agreed with the finding of Anaja and Peter (2022) which revealed that there was a significant relationship between work flexibility and employee performance. Work flexibility practices which allow teachers discharge their duties at their own pace could encourage them to put their efforts in discharging their duties to improve their job performance.

The result of the study revealed that organizational supports is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in consonance with the finding of Salau (2022) which revealed that there was a strong positive relationship between

perceived organizational support and employee performance. This finding could be explained by the fact that organizational supports make teachers to feel valued and empowered to strongly improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Organizational supports provide platform for teachers to receive assistance, encouragement, and resources required to effectively perform their job in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Further result indicated that organizational supports is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Chu, Yu, Litifu, Zhao, Wei, Wang and Wei (2024) which showed that organizational supports had significant relationship with task performance of employees. This is line with the finding of Ikon and Nwoye (2019) which revealed that perceived organizational support had a significant positive relationship with job performance of employees. Organization supports are means of showing cares and assisting teachers to satisfy their needs which they could reciprocate by improving their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

It was found that work flexibility practices and organizational supports are strong predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Dwianto, Darka and Widayatmoko (2023) which showed that job flexibility and organizational supports have strong relationship with employees' job performance/commitment. Work flexibility practices and organizational supports which help teachers to satisfy their physical, social and emotional needs could be responsible for strong prediction of their job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also revealed that work flexibility practices and organizational supports are significant predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Teachers who exercise control over their work schedules and provided with required resources feel happier, fulfilled and more willingness to perform their duties in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that work flexibility practices and organizational supports are strong and predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Work flexibility practices and organizational supports are effective means of improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Teachers could put greater efforts and devote their time in performing their duties, when exposed to work flexibility practices and provided with organizational supports in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Work flexibility practices and organizational supports build a healthy work-life balance which the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of this study:

1. Ministry of Education should develop policy that encourages principals to improve work flexibility practices for high job performance of teachers.
2. Principals should constitute committee to oversee the supports of teachers to improve their job performance.
3. Post Primary Schools Service Commission should organize annual in-service training programmes for principals to enable them update their skills and knowledge on work flexibility practices and organizational supports to improve teachers' job performance.

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